

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Sangwe Clovis**FIRST NAME:** Nchinjoh**PROGRAM CODE:** DIPH**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr Gulma

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
 The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)
 The author used Zotero to insert references
 The author used Grammarly Premium
 The author used Microsoft Word 365 on Windows 10

Five Key Concepts Explored in this Response Paper:

1. Essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 5-14)
3. Literature review (EUCLID 2021, 17-32)
4. Style guide (EUCLID 2021, 24-26)
5. American Vs British English (EUCLID 2021, 27-35)

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ESSENTIAL TOOLS FOR ACADEMIC WRITING**1) INTRODUCTION**

My language of study from elementary education to graduate studies was English. Now, my job in Clinton Health Access Initiative as an associate for routine immunisation in missed communities is principally centred around program designs, strategic and operational planning, program implementation, and health policy advocacy. My new role requires proper use of the English language to effectively disseminate content in ways that will produce the desired outcome. Despite many years of utilising the English language as a tool for written and oral communication in academics, work, and informal contexts, I have faced significant challenges reconciling some complexities surrounding the use of the English language in scientific writing and international program reports. It is challenging to fully grasp and utilise language concepts in a single study period. However, succinct documents like the ACA-401D period [one](#) course [pack](#) (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 1-66) are essential as quick reference tools. I was keen on some concepts, including but not limited to essay writing, plagiarism, literature review, style guide and American Vs British English which I think will sharpen my writing skills and enhance effective communication between my supervisors and me.

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 By the way, delete this particular citation as the mere mention of a piece of work does not call for a citation.

2) ESSAY WRITING

At first sight, this subject sounded basic, but I started wondering whether the word ‘essay’ is an umbrella term for all forms of writings, be it formal or informal. Are letters, manuscripts, thesis considered as essays? What are essays used for, and why is it so valuable for communication? Britannica encyclopaedia described an essay with the following words: ‘Essay, an analytic, interpretative, or critical literary composition usually much shorter and less systematic and formal than a dissertation or thesis and usually dealing with its subject from a limited and often personal point of view.’ (Augustyn 2020).

In history, essays were used to persuade or pass key messages to readers directly. A French writer named Michel de Montaigne called it ‘*Essai*’, meaning to try (Augustyn 2020). His choice of word emphasised the role of this form of composition in attempting to pass personal views to the reader in a persuasive manner. To be compelling enough, one needs to use credible sources and evidence to back up arguments in the essay. This is emphasised in the ACA-401D period one (1) course pack and reads, ‘an academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence.’ (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 1) After all these years of trying to respond to specific questions or passing critical information using essays, especially project reports, I realised there is no one perfect fit approach. My view aligns with the text in this course pack that highlighted vital components of an essay but emphasised that there is no ideal single stepwise approach to writing an essay. (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021)

I think the most challenging part of essay writing is starting the process. This course pack gave quite helpful tips to go around this challenge. It highlights that to begin, it is primordial to understand the question the essay is meant to answer or, better still, the specific objectives of the composition. Having a clear idea of what is expected allows you to objectively search for answers using different approaches such as literature review, desk review, interviews and so on. This will permit sufficient evidence to be obtained to persuade the reader or at least allow the reader to be informed. (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 1)

‘Does the argument make sense? Is it balanced and well researched?’ (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 4) are critical questions in public health essays. As much as essays are centred around personal opinions, public health-related articles need to be driven by evidence. This implies a need to explore opposing information and systematically analyse it before concluding. This logical flow of information allows readers to have round details on the subject matter and better understand your point of view. This era of evidence-based practice and community and person-centred health approach empowers the reader to make more informed decisions about their health and communities. This also applies when developing policy advocacy decks; technical advisers to policymakers depend on balanced arguments to take a stand. The Euclid University emphasising these pertinent questions was exceptionally helpful.

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3) PLAGIARISM

While interacting with this core material and trying to figure out an ideal definition for plagiarism, I stumbled on a text which reads, 'plagiarism is derived from the Latin word 'plagiarius' which means kidnapper.' (Bilal Zaka, Frank Kappe, and Hermann Maurer 2016, 1051) Other brutal words used to describe plagiarism in literature were 'stealing' and 'dishonesty'. (Plagiarism.org 2017) These choices of words, I believe, are meant to emphasise the enormity of plagiarism. However, I think how bad plagiarism is could depend on the composition and institution in question, given that there are so many concepts on this issue, such as self-plagiarism, which may not be interpreted equally in different milieus. As subtle and straightforward as the notion of plagiarism may sound, it is undoubtedly viewed and defined differently in various institutions and works of life. In my professional life, the role of referencing or giving credit to the text owner in producing policy briefs, program reports, and designs is essentially to allow the reader to refer and read further from the primary source. Once the source of my information is cited, it is considered credible even without respecting citation rules and referencing. This is contrary to academics, in which there are strict rules that have to be observed. Therefore, I was elated to see how succinctly Euclid university had laid out vital points that should be observed in academic writing to avoid plagiarism. (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 5–13) Some critical pieces of information which I found to be very valuable included but were not limited to paraphrasing, quotation, and citation is not necessary.

The advent of the internet with available information on a single click makes using software to check plagiarism quite possible. Plagiarism checks usually skip words or sentences in quotation marks and matches phrases found on the text to those in different sources online. This implies that if one rephrases a sentence to use other words, the plagiarism check software may not identify plagiarised phrases. But yet again, there is a pitfall, illustrated by this course pack in 'examples of paraphrasing II' on page 9, which highlights that one can not just change a few words and rephrase; the writing style has to be different. At the same time, the content must reflect the original text. (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 9) 'Examples of paraphrasing III' is quite an eye-opener, though I must admit it takes quite a lot of practice and mastery of core material to be able to paraphrase as such. (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 9)

I found two critical issues fascinating concerning the use of quotations, which authors of the ACA-401D course pack period 1 defined as 'exact words of an author in text.' The first has to do with styling, and the second is when to use it. Using long quotations without quotation marks and displaying them as a separate paragraph is somewhat new to me and truly makes the work clear and presentable. (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7) As wonderful as quotations are to exonerate yourself from critical facts by directly quoting the sources, I noted that it is not recommended to use them too many times, lest the piece of work will not look original. (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7–8)

With the complexities and gravity of plagiarism, especially in academics, I was keen to understand when a citation is not required. So many things are common knowledge

and should not be cited. (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 9–10) I strongly agree that it will not make sense for me to cite a phrase like ‘humans see with eyes’.

4) LITERATURE REVIEW

While I was reading through this course materials, I decided to take a second look by exploring the internet on what exactly literature review is. In the past, I have done a lot of literature reviews to establish a case for action during project proposals. Literature review in my professional life as a public health physician is critical as it provides complete opposing facts on a particular subject. This serves as a basis to establish an actionable plan for further research to contextualise and develop a situational analysis or take decisions based on evidence in the literature. As Shona McCombes puts it, ‘A good literature review doesn’t just summarise sources—it analyses, synthesises, and critically evaluates to give a clear picture of the state of knowledge on the subject.’(McCombes 2019) One of the significant challenges with literature review is access to relevant information. With the advent of the internet, many scholarly articles, journals, and books are open sources. Availability of so much information with a single click raises a new challenge of deciphering which is truly relevant to the subject of interest. Analytic skills are critical to select and use available information based on evidence.

However, this course period focused more on the writing skills needed to word and communicate findings on literature review properly. (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 17–23) The importance of correctly wording and punctuating sentences in a literature review can not be overemphasised. An oral form of communication has an advantage over a written counter-part because the display of emotions can give a passive, neutral or active feel to the message. Body language, in general, can make oral presentations to be very interesting and well understood even if the use of the English language is not optimal. However, the structure, grammar, proper punctuation and logical flow of text in a literature review can make the work uninteresting to read or even hard to understand. I, therefore, consider this aspect of the course to be of great relevance.

5) STYLE GUIDE

I have been implicitly using style guides for different reasons without being conscious of the critical role that it has to play. I am pretty conversant with using the word ‘template’ as a guide to the structure, of which, thanks to this course pack, I now understand they are style guides. (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021) Though I must admit, the templates were primarily designed by institution heads to enhance communication and ease understanding of technical notes and reports. I was unaware of some standardised style guides that one can use without necessarily creating one de novo. The key take-home message is that grammar, vocabulary, and correct punctuation are not enough to make a good composition (technical writing, manuscripts, reports). (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 24–25) Other elements such as word limits, use of abbreviations, amongst others that make up the writing style and structure are equally important.

6) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

Cameroon is a former British colony, and as such, one of her official languages is British English. However, both American and British English is allowed in an official and academic milieu. I have never been confronted with the need to choose either style, so I never really bother to ensure my writing sticks to one. Realising the level of perfection expected of me in this post-graduate study, I must commend the course instructors for carefully selecting and illustrating the most complex and confusing aspects of both language writing styles.

7) CONCLUSION

Over the next couple of years, my academic journey will require lots of writing and communication; undoubtedly, I need to sharpen my writing skills. The art of academic writing involves practice to grasp the concept entirely. Considering how demanding the Doctorate in International Public Health program is, a quick writing reference tool will be precious. The ACA-401D period one(1) course pack met my needs and expectations in this regard.

I will be keen to go through the course material as often as possible and print and use it as a quick reference tool. I strongly recommend this for all students beginning their graduate academic journey.

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